

**THE PECULARITIES OF ANGRY YOUNG MEN MOVEMENT IN “ LUCKY JIM” BY
KINGSLEY AMISS**

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Annotation: *“Lucky Jim” by Kingsley Amiss is a campus novel that describes the social class conflicts and the distress that the British youth went through after World War II. The following article draws some views about the ideals and way of thinking of the Angry Young Men movement, which are portrayed in “Lucky Jim” by Kingsley Amiss.*

Keywords: *campus novel, “Lucky Jim”, “Angry Young Men,” “Look Back in Anger” social class, protagonist*

The "angry young men" were a group of mostly working and middle class British playwrights and novelists who became prominent in the 1950s. They showed their hatred towards the long established social class system of Britain, and their writings frequently expressed anger and frustration as the postwar reforms failed to meet exalted aspirations for genuine change. Even though there were brilliant minds in the society, everything worked for the benefit of the rich. [2],

The movement was important because it expressed a common sentiment in post-WWII Britain. The writers who tapped into this sentiment felt it as well. People were tired of the same policies and ideas and the split between the lower classes and upper classes seemed wider than ever. When readers explore works written during this movement, it's possible to feel and understand their discontent and disillusionment. John Osborne is considered to be the father of the Angry Young Men movement. His work “Look Back in Anger” is considered to express the interests of the movement.

Kingsley Amiss was one of the the well known figures of the movement, whose wrtings regarding the period are invaluable. “ Lucky Jim” actually brought Amis into the forefront of the literary scene of that time and gave him that instant limelight and renowned elevating him above other Angry Men of that period. Jim Dixon’s battle and rebellion against the moderate foundation and conventions of scholastic England is both interesting and comical. Amis acknowledges the assessments that the novel Lucky Jim had been a class-cognizant novel and that it depicted social changes attributed to the social changes in war ravaged England. The portrayal of the class framework and the interactions between Jim with the rest of the characters specifically his personal views and evaluations is actually a reflection of society of that period..

From the beginning till the end, it is not difficult to realize the fact that Jim restricts his emotions. The story starts with the conversation between Jim and Professor. The protagonist Jim Dixon has to say good words about him and he is obliged to accept each word by Welch, because he has to secure his job; otherwise he will be left out of job. Jim's hatred and disillusionment toward the bourgeois class are clear from his facial expressions. At a point he comes across a fight with Bertrand, who is the son of Professor Welch. But this situation also worked for Bertrand, even though this guy was arrogant and cruel. Here it can be seen that the elite class of the society got the upper hand in every angle. Mr. Welch indirectly forces Jim to behave corresponding to conformity despite Jim's frustration. This frustration increases anger in the novel.

"It was a perfect title, in that it crystallized the article's niggling mindlessness, its funereal parade of yawn-enforcing facts, the pseudo-light it threw upon non-problems." [1]

This quotation, thought by Dixon in Chapter 1 as he is riding in the car with Professor Welch, expresses Dixon's feelings about his own academic article, and scholarship in general. The quotation asserts that not only is Dixon's article—and academia in general—obscure, but also condemns the article for masquerading as something useful and revealing. This added offense of posturing prepares us for Dixon's hatred of academia and the false posturing of others throughout the rest of the novel. The quotation is also a good early example of one type of linguistic humor in the novel, which periodically uses multiple clauses to increase the ridiculousness of a situation. Finally, the quotation stands as our first evidence in *Lucky Jim* of Dixon's capacity for self-deprecating humor. He does not spare himself in his sardonic identifications of pomposity.

"The sight of her seemed an irresistible attack on his own habits, standards, and ambitions: something designed to put him in his place for good."

Dixon thinks this quotation to himself when he first sees Christine Callaghan at the Welches' home in Chapter 4. The quotation is the first indication of Dixon's tormented feelings about Christine, who he is tempted by but who is unavailable to him. Christine is unavailable not only because she is currently dating Bertrand, but also because she is in a different class than Dixon or the kind of women he dates. Many parts of the Welches' artsy party seem designed to put Dixon in his place, but, significantly, it is only Christine who arouses this kind of class anxiety in him.

"Consciousness was upon him before he could get out of the way."

This quotation comes at the beginning of a long passage describing Dixon's hangover at the beginning of Chapter 6. The quotation is a good example of how comedy works in *Lucky Jim*, as the humor of this particular quotation lies in its twisting an ordinary phrase into something absurd. Dixon's humor often works this way in the novel, taking trite or clichéd language of others, then inverting it on itself.

The passage in which this quotation appears describes at length Dixon's feelings upon waking up with a nasty hangover, and this is also indicative of the humor of the novel, where comedic lines are used to underscore comedic situations.

"...his theory that nice things are nicer than nasty ones."

Both Lucky Jim and Kingsley Amis were often evoked in service of, or mentioned in association with, a shifting, or even revolutionary, atmosphere in England after World War II. Quotations such as the one above, however, reveal the underlying fidelity to stasis and simplicity in Dixon's philosophy. Dixon knows what he likes and what he doesn't like, and his problem is learning to act on those instincts, not to re-evaluating them. This particular excerpt is also indicative of the final comic justice at the end of the novel, whereby the characters are rewarded for doing what they want.[4]

As "Lucky Jim" is an academic novel, the events are related to college events and study. Here also, Dixon is reluctant to accept Mr. Welch, but he does so. Because Professor Welch is the person who can fire Dixon. Jim is discontented because he is an amateur in his job, because his identity is undermined and in the novel he is stuck in a social environment in which he is extremely dissatisfied.

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